

Transformative & immersive storytelling design

Co-design session

Designed by Denise de Spirito, Irene Fiesoli, Eleonora D'Ascenzi

Introduction

TISD, Co-design session

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The tool we are presenting is based on an “undisciplined” methodology (DASD), in which multiple disciplines—Design, Performance Art, Social Sciences, and Digital technologies—are intertwined to design transformative immersive storytelling experiences.

DASD will guide you on a creative journey through the 4C process: **Care, Content, Context, and Change.**

These pillars will be your allies in uncovering new perspectives, overturning points of view, and raising awareness around body acceptance issues that matter to you, paving the way for storytelling that **not only informs, but transforms.**

Tool Rules

Step 1

Setup

STEP 1: Brainstorming + Care

1. Form groups of Min. 2 / Max. 4 people.
2. Give each participant a marker, each in a different color.
3. Take one "Brainstorming" canvas for each group.

DURATION: 30 min.

Rules

STEP 1: Brainstorming + Care

Start of the "BRAINSTORMING" session

1. Each participant in the working group can draw or write on the canvas, feeling free to express their opinion.
2. In this step, you can use the card decks: "Your body" & "Other people's bodies".

After completing the "Brainstorming" board, fill in the Care canvas.

enjoy your work!

Materials to print - Step 1

“Brainstorming” canvas

Express yourself freely! Two card decks are associated with this step: “Your body” and “Other people’s bodies.”
If you have any questions or difficulties, talk to a tutor.

The body I am (NOT)

Listen

Experience it actively

Contribute

30min.

“Your body” card deck

“Other people's bodies” card deck

"Care" canvas

Starting from the "Brainstorming" board, use the "Care" canvas to choose the theme at the core of the project.

If you have any questions or difficulties, talk to a tutor.

"CARE" **What/who do I want to take care of?**

Theme: _____

Listen

Experience it actively

Contribute

30min.

Tool Rules

Step 2

Setup

STEP 2: Starting Concept

1. Together with all group members, choose a provisional title.
2. Place the **STARTING CONCEPT** worksheet so that it is reachable by everyone.
3. Hand out one numbered card to each participant.

Rules

STEP 2 Starting Concept

We can get started!

The participant with **Card no. 1** rolls the (DASDO) die and must draw from the “DASD Suggestions” decks one card for each discipline. Since each side of the DASDO includes two disciplines, the maximum number of cards each participant will draw is always 2.

(E.g., if the die lands on **Ar/So**, draw one card from the Ar deck and one from the So deck.)

1. Following the order of the card numbers (1, 2, 3, 4), each participant, during their turn, may:

- Freely draw something related to the theme chosen in the Care canvas.
- Suggest a change, propose a solution, or ask a question. *[e.g., What material is it made of?]*
- Add a comment preceded by the symbol (+) *(e.g., + recyclable plastic)*

REQUIRED:

1. Draw the cards for each turn.
2. In every turn, each participant must express their own idea (write, draw).
3. At the end, fill in the “DASD LEVEL” line.

enjoy your work!

Materials to print - Step 2

Numbered cards for participants

Hand out randomly.

"D.A.S.D. Suggestions" card deck

Bite-sized suggestions and information for each discipline.

<p>Di</p>	<p>Did you know that digital immersivity goes beyond the boundaries of reality?</p> <p>Di</p>	<p>You can choose an unconventional point of view.</p> <p>Design it to spark debate!</p> <p>Di</p>	<p>In the digital world, taking others' perspectives allows us to move beyond personal boundaries.</p> <p>Di</p>	<p>Digital doesn't replace reality!</p> <p>Or maybe it does? Or maybe it doesn't?</p> <p>Di</p>	<p>Leave your body behind to live in someone else's.</p> <p>Di</p>
<p>Ar</p>	<p>Did you know there are strategies artists can use to overcome the traditional boundaries between the stage and the audience?</p> <p>Ar</p>	<p>Introduce new narrative perspectives... unexpected ones!</p> <p>Ar</p>	<p>"If we could put ourselves in others' shoes - so much so that we felt others as if they were ourselves - we wouldn't need rules or laws anymore!"</p> <p>Ar</p>	<p>When the experience ends... the debate begins!!!</p> <p>Ar</p>	<p>How can you perceive through your body?</p> <p>Ar</p>
<p>So</p>	<p>Did you know that immersing someone in a different context helps them understand other people's points of view?</p> <p>So</p>	<p>Flip the point of view and spark empathy!</p> <p>So</p>	<p>"You can't judge anyone unless you've walked in their shoes."</p> <p>So</p>	<p>Go beyond prejudice! Or try to fight it, disrupt it.</p> <p>So</p>	<p>"The mind thinks, while the heart already knows."</p> <p>So</p>
<p>De</p>	<p>Did you know that a sensory experience can transport you into a completely different world?</p> <p>De</p>	<p>Challenge traditional conventions!</p> <p>De</p>	<p>Design by understanding other people's needs as if they were your own.</p> <p>De</p>	<p>Tell stories to inform and to... transform!</p> <p>De</p>	<p>Design to evoke emotions!</p> <p>De</p>

10 cards per subject

<p>Empathize without necessarily relying on words.</p> <p>Di</p>	<p>Imagine a VIRTUAL experience.</p> <p>Di</p>	<p>Participant, NOT an avatar!</p> <p>Di</p>	<p>You're capable of innovating!</p> <p>Di</p>	<p>What are the limits of virtual technologies?</p> <p>Di</p>
<p>"Empathy is an actor's privilege!"</p> <p>Ar</p>	<p>Explore a theme through a... PERFORMANCE!</p> <p>Ar</p>	<p>Participant, NOT a spectator!</p> <p>Ar</p>	<p>You're capable of moving people!</p> <p>Ar</p>	<p>What are the limits of performative art?</p> <p>Ar</p>
<p>Empathy = "to feel within"</p> <p>So</p>	<p>Explore a theme through other people's stories.</p> <p>So</p>	<p>Participant, NOT a study subject!</p> <p>So</p>	<p>You have a strong understanding of others!</p> <p>So</p>	<p>What are the limits of the social sciences?</p> <p>So</p>
<p>Empathic design is inclusive design.</p> <p>De</p>	<p>Explore a theme through storytelling design.</p> <p>De</p>	<p>Participant, NOT a user!</p> <p>De</p>	<p>You can imagine and give shape to your ideas!</p> <p>De</p>	<p>What are the limits of communication design?</p> <p>De</p>

"Starting Concept" canvas

If you have any questions or difficulties, talk to a tutor.

Write the concept name/title here.

DASD LEVEL!

At the end, mark with an X how much each discipline was involved in the concept.

Mark it on the 0–5 scale.

Digital

0 1 2 3 4 5

Performative
Art

0 1 2 3 4 5

Social
Sciences

0 1 2 3 4 5

Design

0 1 2 3 4 5

DA(S)DO

Instructions for building the DASD die

Material:

- **White die**
(https://www.amazon.it/dp/B075898DQD?ref=ppx_yo2ov_dt_b_product_details&th=1)
- **Permanent marker**

Rules:

On each face of the white die, draw the abbreviations for the discipline combinations, as shown in the figure beside it.

Face 1

Face 2

Face 3

Face 4

Face 5

Face 6

Tool Rules

Step 3

Rules

STEP 3: Concept 4C

Let's get started!

1. Write the title again or, if needed, update it.
2. Write WHAT/WHO the group is taking care of.
3. Following the order of the numbered Cards (1, 2, 3, 4) and keeping in mind what was developed in the "Starting Concept" board, each participant, during their turn, can:

- Freely draw or write something in the Context, Content, or Change box.
- Add a comment preceded by the (+) symbol.
[e.g., + recyclable plastic].

REQUIRED:

1. In every turn, it is mandatory to write, draw, or express an idea.
2. All the boxes on the canvas (Context, Content, and Change) must be filled in.

Enjoy your work

Setup

STEP 3: Concept 4C

This step allows you to further develop the concept you began working on in the previous "Starting Concept" board.

Using the CONCEPT 4C canvas, define the Context, Content, and Change of your project concept.

"Concept 4C" canvas.

If you have any questions or difficulties, talk to a tutor.

Write the concept title here.

Content

Which story do you want to tell?

Context

How do you want to tell it?

Change

What behavioral change do you want to trigger?

CARE

DASD LEVEL!

At the end, indicate whether there are any updates, compared to the previous canvas, to the disciplines involved.

Write the corresponding codes in the cell: Digital (DI), Performative Art (ART), Social Sciences (SO), Design (DE).

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